

D5.4. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Final Report

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V1	Burcu Kiper (CHX)	26/05/2026	Final version for submission

List of acronyms

Acronym	Full name
EC	European Commission
CHX	Crowdhelix
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
NEBS	Network of European Blue Schools
WP	Work Package
RTOs	Research and technology organisations
YTU	Yıldız Technical University

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Background about the SHORE Project

SHORE strives to increase ocean literacy by engaging students and teachers to implement the Mission Ocean & Waters' objectives through activities and collaborative projects in schools.

Within this project, the project partners craft trainings and educational materials in line with blue curricula for schools located in the Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Danube River, and Rhine River. Participating schools secure grants to support the implementation of their blue projects. The most outstanding school projects are awarded "Ocean Ambassador of the Year".

Beyond awarding grants, SHORE serves as a comprehensive resource hub and a bridge between researchers, local stakeholders, and schools in the regional areas.

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the SHORE Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101112815. SHORE is part of the EU Mission Ocean & Waters".

The aim of this document is to present the final report on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community on the Crowdhelix (CHX) platform. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix, a virtual collaboration community established on the CHX open innovation platform, is a fundamental aspect of the dissemination, exploitation and communication strategies developed both during and after the SHORE Project. Over the last 3 years of the SHORE project, the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix has reached out to and engaged with various stakeholders, increased its user base and the number of subscribing organisations, and fostered cross-collaboration with the SHORE project's sister projects and other EU-funded Mission Ocean-related projects. In this regard, the community acted as a knowledge exchange network and digital platform, bringing together stakeholders from cross-cutting sectors into its sphere of influence to maximise the SHORE project's impact. The deliverable presents the final report, outlining the community setup, members, activities, features, and Helix-related events.

As part of the SHORE project's dissemination, communication, and exploitation, the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community provides project objectives, activities, partners, public deliverables, videos, and other results to all stakeholders identified in the project, with a commitment to preserving the community for up to 5 years beyond the project lifetime. Activities of the Helix include actively managing the community to increase its reach to relevant experts, organisations and projects, including the SHORE partners, sister project representatives, Crowdhelix network members and other institutions, encouraging continued collaboration on the Helix, organising clustering events and webinars, and delivering impact in line with the Helix strategy.

Non-technical summary

This document outlines the final report of the Mission Ocean and Water Helix community - one of the communication, dissemination and exploitation tools of the SHORE Project, which is part of the European Union's Mission Ocean & Waters initiative.

The SHORE Project aims to empower students and teachers to become advocates for the oceans by enhancing their understanding of these vital ecosystems.

The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community operates on the Crowdhelix platform, serving as a space for collaboration and knowledge sharing among various stakeholders. Over the past three years, this community has successfully engaged a diverse group of participants, broadened its network, and fostered collaboration with other Mission Ocean projects.

The final report details the community's formation, its members, the activities it has organised, and the events it has hosted. The Helix community plays a crucial role in raising awareness of the project's goals and providing valuable resources for anyone interested in ocean literacy. In its commitment to sustainability, Crowdhelix (CHX) aims to maintain its efforts for at least five years after the project concludes. Activities include closely managing the community's collaboration, increasing its membership and reach to relevant experts and organisations, hosting webinars and events, and ensuring that the community's mission continues to thrive even after the project's completion.

1. Introduction

1.1. Aim of the Deliverable, Overview and Structure

The deliverable 5.4. The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Final Report outlines key developments, updates, results, and the impact of the Helix community and its related activities, while showcasing various analytics. The deliverable is structured around i) the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community setup, including key developments and updates from the platform. This section provides an overview of the Mission Ocean & Waters community's progress achieved throughout the SHORE project, highlighting collaborative efforts and strategic initiatives ii) Helix activities for various stakeholders, such as clustering activities aimed at fostering connections with related projects, enhancing knowledge sharing, and disseminating project outcomes among scientists, researchers, and other critical stakeholders.

The deliverable, developed as part of Task 5.4: Stakeholder Engagement and Clustering Activities, and Task 5.5: Setup and Management of the Mission Ocean Helix within Work Package (WP) 5: Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach, outlines how the virtual community and cluster were managed. The Helix aimed to facilitate collaboration among expert users from academia, education, and training in the fields of blue economy and marine ecosystems. It also emphasised connections with other funded projects, knowledge exchange, and the implementation of sustainability measures that extend beyond the SHORE project's duration.

1.2. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix in the SHORE Project: Relevance and Impact

For European-funded research and innovation projects, it is essential to accelerate impact and ensure sustainability. Research and innovation communities and consortia must collaborate and engage in activities and initiatives that link research outputs to real-world needs. This approach is vital for the effective transfer of knowledge and technology, as well as for contributing to innovation and competitiveness. The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix initiative has been developed on the Crowdhelix platform to support the SHORE project throughout its various development stages, including the post-project phase.

Crowdhelix is a global open-innovation network and platform (<https://crowdhelix.com/>) that connects academic and industry stakeholders to promote collaborative research and dissemination. It has a reach of over 20,000 researchers, innovators, and business leaders on its platform. This membership base includes over 500 universities and businesses across over 50 thematic communities (Helixes), with the wider collaborative network reaching more than 400,000 research and innovation actors through its members and sector partners. These connections support communities such as Mission Ocean & Waters Helix in their collaborative research and development initiatives.

A Helix community brings together individuals and organisations to enhance collaboration and partnerships. It operates as a virtual platform where organisations

can subscribe and network with stakeholders. By promoting EU-funded projects, it serves as a repository for Key Exploitable Results. The Helix also facilitates matchmaking and clustering activities, helping users identify relevant collaborators. Users can share information about funding opportunities, events, and workshops to stay informed. Additionally, its recommender engine effectively profiles and connects innovations to global end-users. This methodological framework, utilised in the SHORE Project, is summarised in the figure below.

Mission Ocean & Waters Helix is an international virtual community that brings together experts from research and technology organisations, educational institutions, businesses, funding agencies, and civil society organisations focused on the blue economy, water, and marine ecosystems. It highlights the SHORE project as its key initiative, serving a network of **887 experts from 323 organisations across 46 countries**.

Figure 1- Helix Impact Model

SHORE project was disseminated through **(1) the CrowdHelix platform**; tools including the Helix community, other aligned communities, resource centre, funding searches and dissemination channels links **(2) Impact Acceleration Team**; facilitating connections and collaboration for consortium development and delivering impact events **(3) CrowdHelix network**; made up of research and innovation organisations, industry, commercial actors, and civil society. Through interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration among stakeholders, the Helix Impact Model leverages virtual communities to drive impact in EU-funded projects.

As outlined in the grant agreement, the primary objective of the Helix community is to serve as a knowledge-exchange **network and interaction platform** that brings together stakeholders from various sectors to enhance the project's impact.

As detailed in the D5.2 Plan for Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach, Mission Ocean & Waters Helix serves as a channel for engaging the target group of **“European and international projects and initiatives”**. This group includes organisations, projects, and funding bodies at both the European and international levels, as well as SHORE's sister projects. In line with the SHORE project's clustering activities, the Helix aims to integrate other funded projects into its network, as evidenced by the profiling of projects such as ProBleu, Blue LightS, and Plastic Pirates. As described in the D5.3 Stakeholder Engagement Report, the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix is also one of the channels for the stakeholder group: **scientists and researcher community** to:

- Facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration
- Share and discuss research findings
- Integrate cutting-edge research into project initiatives.

As a key stakeholder group, scientists and researchers contribute to the development of informed educational content and to enhancing the credibility of SHORE initiatives through their engagement in SHORE project activities. To this end, the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community has implemented the Helix strategy to target this stakeholder group through collaboration opportunities, knowledge transfer events, and the dissemination of project results to the CHX's network of research and technology organisations and +20,000 users.

The Helix provides a valuable networking opportunity for educators, researchers, and advocates dedicated to ocean literacy. This virtual community facilitates the sharing of best practices in education, enabling educators to access shared resources and innovative teaching methods. By effectively communicating project results, including public deliverables and events, the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix supports the objectives of promoting Mission Ocean and Waters' goals. Furthermore, it contributes to the SHORE project's sustainability, as the community is set to operate for up to 5 years after the project concludes.

2. Development of the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

The Mission Ocean & Water Helix was successfully aligned with the SHORE project throughout its duration. As part of the wider Helix community structure on the Crowdhelix platform, as shown below, Mission Ocean & Waters Helix is closely linked with other Helixes in the fields of the blue economy, water, and marine ecosystems, as well as with Helixes on the themes of inclusion, citizen science, and society. The Helix also belongs to the Horizon Europe Mission Helix cluster, which includes cancer, soil, climate, and smart cities.

Figure 2- Helix Communities Related to Horizon Europe Clusters and Horizon Europe Missions

Figure 3- Aligned Helix Communities to SHORE

These Helixes bring together experts and innovation professionals from academia and industry to collaborate on shared challenges and opportunities. By connecting this broad research and innovation ecosystem, the platform offers core functionalities that support engagement and collaboration:

- Collaboration opportunities posting (for new proposals)
- Dissemination opportunities posting (for ongoing projects)
- Results posting (for ongoing and past projects in the field)
- Announcements for trainings, events, research, and studies
- Expertise offers by researchers and organisations
- Search engine for identifying suitable collaborators
- Interaction with experts and organisations through messaging and comment features

The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix is an important “multiplier” of the SHORE project’s messages and outputs. It supports collaboration and the dissemination of key results to accelerate the impact of its community of specialists in the fields of the blue economy, water, and marine ecosystems.

The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix is visible to all organisations and users on the Crowdhelix platform and has been promoted to over 10,777 platform users. Consortium members who are profiled on the Helix can utilise the platform for matchmaking and dissemination at no cost for the duration of the project. During the Helix launch, a special announcement was created and included in the notification emails Crowdhelix sent to all its members. Additionally, the Helix launch was announced to platform users in a dedicated post. All Crowdhelix users have access to all the posts, including the

Mission Ocean & Waters Helix posts. Consortium members were onboarded to the platform.

SHORE

Joana Soares
for Crowdfunder
2 yr since in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Citizen Science

Invitation to Join the Mission Oceans Helix Community!

Seeking collaborator:
Domain Expert Investor Community Participant

Seeking expertise:

- Bioeconomy
- Ocean literacy
- Ocean
- Conservation-restoration
- Secondary schools
- Marine restoration
- Ecological restoration and conservation
- Atlantic ocean
- Blue biotech
- Blue bioeconomy
- Wetland restoration
- Primary schools
- Teachers education
- Coastal waters
- Ocean resources
- Teachers training
- Ocean research
- Blue bioresources
- Mission ocean and waters
- Blue schools

We are pleased to invite you to join the 'Mission Oceans' community. The Mission Oceans Helix is an initiative stemming from the SHORE project, funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe funding programme.

The SHORE project is part of the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters. Its goal is to enhance ocean literacy by engaging students and teachers in collaborative projects and activities that align with Mission Ocean's objectives at the school level.

By joining the Helix, you can follow the project's advancements, activities, events, and results as well as collaborate with your peers. Within the Helix, you can share and join specific collaboration opportunities related to this topic. You can also invite any stakeholders outside of the Network who may be interested in this field, and whom you trust to participate.

To join the Mission Oceans Helix visit <https://crowdfunder.com/helixes...> and click "Follow". You will then be notified of new opportunities posted, according to your chosen notification settings.

SHORE IS AN EU MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEANS AND WATERS PROJECT. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101112815.

 Funded by the European Union

Figure 4- Invitation to join the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

Mission Ocean & Waters Helix is managed by the Crowdhelix impact acceleration team and is scientifically led by the SHORE project coordinator, Prof.Dr. Afşin Çetinkaya. While the Helix managers focus on the community's technical and collaborative aspects, the scientific leaders are responsible for directing Helix's scientific goals to align with the SHORE project's strategic objectives.

Mission Ocean & Waters

Increasing the awareness of ocean literacy among society, with a specific focus on empowering students as agents of change

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Background

The Blue Economy, which encompasses economic activities related to oceans, seas and coasts, is vital to life on Earth. However, the rapid degradation of marine and freshwater ecosystems poses challenges that threaten the well-being of European citizens. This underlines the urgency outlined in the EU Green Deal and the Mission "Restore Our Ocean and Waters" by 2030.

Challenges remain in promoting ocean literacy, especially among young people, as marine ecosystems face increasing threats. Deliberative democracy, social innovation, citizen science and awareness-raising campaigns are key tools. Recognising youth as catalysts for change, initiatives should integrate life-changing projects into school curricula and promote grassroots and international mobilisation. Communities need to be empowered with knowledge that fosters an understanding of the importance of the ocean and individual impacts on the marine environment.

The evolving concept of environmental education emphasises a holistic approach to sustainable development. Coordination, engagement at local and international levels, and mobilisation across all sectors are essential for a 'Decade of Action' to achieve the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals. Despite progress, a comprehensive approach to the challenges remains crucial.

Key Project

Empower Students as the Agents of Change (SHORE) is a 36-month HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions funded by the European Union.

SHORE aims to improve ocean literacy by involving students and teachers in the implementation of Mission Ocean objectives through collaborative projects and activities at the school level. This initiative will develop training materials and educational courses aligned with blue curricula for schools in the Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Danube and Rhine regions. Participating schools will have the opportunity to apply for grants to support the implementation of their blue projects. The most outstanding school project will be awarded the prestigious title of Ocean Ambassador of the Year. Most importantly, SHORE aims to act as a comprehensive resource hub, facilitating links between researchers, local stakeholders and schools in each regional area. Yıldız Technical University (Türkiye) is leading a diverse consortium behind SHORE. Comprising 14 partners, each bringing different expertise, innovation and experience, the project is committed to promoting ocean literacy across our five regional areas.

Mission Oceans Helix

The Mission Oceans Helix is an international open innovation community of experts from academia, education and training in the blue economy, water and marine ecosystems and related fields.

Launched with a specific focus on driving impact, leveraging resources and facilitating knowledge dissemination, the Helix plays a critical role in supporting the broader Mission Oceans community's goal of improving the health and sustainability of our oceans and waters.

Seeking collaborators for Mission Ocean & Waters projects?
Post a new Opportunity in this Helix

[Create Post](#)

- [887 Experts](#) [View All](#)
- [323 Organisations](#) [View All](#)
- [46 Countries](#) [View All](#)

EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters

2:08

EU Mission Restore our Ocean & Waters

Dr. Burcu Kiper
Helix Manager

[Message](#)

The ocean's potential lies not only in its depths but in collective excellence. In open innovation, we find a compass that guides us towards sustainable solutions and a shared commitment to the restoration and protection of our precious ocean and waters.

Prof. Afşin ÇETİNKAYA
Helix Leader

Organisations [Join](#)

Yıldız Technical University
Leading Organisation

Figure 5- Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Landing Page on CHX Platform

The following activities and key performance indicators were set for the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix throughout the duration of the project:

- a) Invitation to consortium partners, CHX membership base and other relevant stakeholders to join the Helix following the update of the Helix description with the project logo, information, links and resources
- b) Organisation of two Helix events
- c) Organisation of webinars and clustering events
- d) Inclusion of more than 250 members in the Helix community
- e) Impact delivery in line with the Helix strategy (including supporting dissemination events and building collaboration through the platform).

2.1. Benefits of the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix for the SHORE Project Consortium

The Helix innovation community offers numerous benefits for the SHORE project consortium and partner organisations, particularly in enhancing collaboration and supporting clustering activities. Project partners can publish new collaboration opportunities, showcase their results for further exploitation, connect with a diverse range of stakeholders, and promote events, conferences, and other project-related activities to strengthen their dissemination efforts. This community has the added advantage of including subject matter experts who support innovations emerging from EU-funded projects.

The benefits across the whole communication, dissemination and exploitation domains can be summarised as:

Table 1- Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Benefits

Function	Means
Communication tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Posting opportunities for collaboration on research and projects. - Reaching out to over 20,000 experts and organisations across more than 50 communities. - Highlighting SHORE as the key project within the Helix.
Dissemination tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Publishing research and project results for wider distribution. - Providing a platform for external stakeholders to join and collaborate, creating clustering opportunities.
Exploitation tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishing connections with industry stakeholders, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), large enterprises, and potential investors. - Offering access to roundtable discussions and dedicated matchmaking events.

3. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Community Growth and Expansion

The CHX impact acceleration team worked on expanding the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community to engage with experts beyond the consortium members, aiming to build a strong community. The stakeholder identification and analysis conducted and reported in the Stakeholder Engagement Report (D5.3) informed the selection of organisations and experts to target for community expansion and growth.

In addition to the researchers and organisations within the Crowdhelix network, individuals outside the network who are interested in the activities and collaborative opportunities generated in the Helix were given free access to the platform. This limited access has allowed them to engage with opportunities posted by members on the platform and have direct contact with Helix members. Additionally, they have the option to leave comments to express their interest in specific opportunities, subject to moderation by the Crowdhelix team. As a curated platform, it ensures that the most relevant opportunities are published and connections are made.

The CHX impact acceleration team also focused on expanding the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community by engaging with other Mission Ocean projects and related EU-funded projects. This work was conducted in accordance with the communication, dissemination, and outreach plan (D5.2) and the clustering plan outlined in WP5, supported networking, broader dissemination, and the exploitation of project results, and contributed to the project's post-completion impact objectives.

As part of its clustering activities, CHX utilised its platform tools and features to promote the sister projects of the SHORE project: [BlueLightS](#) and [ProBleu](#). The CHX impact acceleration team collaborated closely with the coordinators and DEC representatives from all three projects to carry out digital networking activities on its platform. They also invited representatives from the sister projects to join the Mission Ocean and Waters Helix as trusted collaborators.

4. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Framework

Based on the Helix Impact Model described in the preceding sections, the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix framework, components and features are detailed below.

4.1. Stakeholder Identification and Profiling

Stakeholder identification and categorisation for the SHORE project and the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community are detailed in the D5.3 Stakeholder Engagement Report, which identifies primary and secondary stakeholder categories. The primary stakeholders of the SHORE project include:

- Educational institutions, teachers and students
- Governmental and non-governmental organisations
- Scientist and the research community
- Regional and local communities

- Industry
- Media

The secondary stakeholders of the SHORE project include

- Funding and grant providers
- International organisations
- Technology partners

Identifying and profiling various stakeholder groups allowed CHX to effectively structure and invite relevant participants to join the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix. To ensure engagement with diverse stakeholders from the SHORE groups within the Helix ecosystem, users are encouraged to create and update their platform profiles. This involves specifying their organisational type, sector, and/or scientific expertise. Additionally, users can assign free-form keywords that reflect their expertise, research areas, and interests. These keywords serve as the foundation for matching stakeholders with relevant opportunities on the platform. With this feature, CHX can automatically suggest valuable connections and keep stakeholders informed about opportunities aligned with their expertise.

Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community's membership typology is as follows:

Figure 6-Typology of Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Stakeholders

Research and technology organisations (RTOs) represent the largest share of membership, reflecting the strong academic and research orientation of the Helix community. SMEs constitute the second-largest group, indicating meaningful engagement with the industry and innovation sectors within the community. The remaining membership comprises corporates (3%), associations (3%), and specialist organisations (2%), indicating that whilst the Helix is rooted in the research and innovation ecosystem, it also attracts a cross-sectoral range of stakeholders with complementary expertise and interests in ocean and water sustainability.

Figure 7-Location of Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Users

In terms of geographical spread, as illustrated in Figure 7, Mission Ocean & Waters Helix has a global reach with member organisations in Europe and beyond. The top ten countries by total users are Great Britain, Türkiye, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Ireland, Greece, Finland, Israel, and Norway. The presence of Türkiye and Italy – both SHORE country hub nations among the top ten countries by user subscription reflects the impact of the SHORE project in different regional contexts.

	Helix		
1.	Mission Ocean & Waters	GB	178
2.	Mission Ocean & Waters	TR	127
3.	Mission Ocean & Waters	IT	71
4.	Mission Ocean & Waters	ES	56
5.	Mission Ocean & Waters	PT	48
6.	Mission Ocean & Waters	IE	46
7.	Mission Ocean & Waters	GR	38
8.	Mission Ocean & Waters	FI	34
9.	Mission Ocean & Waters	IL	31
10.	Mission Ocean & Waters	NO	28

Figure 8-Top ten countries by user subscription on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

4.2. Engagement Strategy

D5.3 Stakeholder Engagement Report, based on thorough stakeholder mapping and categorisation, outlines a comprehensive strategy for engaging with stakeholders of different types according to their roles, expectations, interests, and concerns. This strategy includes key messages tailored to each stakeholder group, recommended engagement channels, and the potential impact of these interactions. It specifies which stakeholder groups the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community should target and engage. According to the report, the community is particularly beneficial for **(1) scientists and researchers, (2) Funding and grant providers (including sister projects), (3) International organisations.**

As a primary stakeholder group in the SHORE project, the scientific and research community was a key focus of the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix. Their expectations for engagement included participation in platforms for knowledge exchange and collaboration. The platform's opportunity and results posting features directly contributed to this target group's interest in sharing and discussing research findings. International initiatives targeted by the project also anticipated involvement in forums and events. The information, results, and resources shared on the Helix aimed to raise awareness of global ocean literacy initiatives and attract this stakeholder group. Additionally, funding and grant providers, including the Mission Ocean projects and related initiatives, benefited from active collaboration with the community, as the Helix sought to create connections with other blue projects and initiatives.

A variety of tools on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix were made available to its members to promote interaction and collaboration. The included:

The Resources Tool: The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix landing page offers communication and dissemination channels, along with essential materials such as the SHORE project website and its social media platforms (LinkedIn, YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, and X (formerly Twitter)) as well as communication materials such as the project brochure, Zenodo community access, and a newsletter subscription. Additionally, this section features links to sister projects, ProBleu and BlueLightS, along with resources from the Mission Ocean & Waters initiative and the Network of European Blue Schools. It also provides access to documents and strategies related to the blue economy, oceans, and waters.

Figure 9-Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Resources

Helix Leader, Helix Manager, Helix Organisations Profiling and Who’s in the Helix Feature: This feature provided opportunities for members to familiarise themselves with the information on the consortium, Helix contact persons and improved visibility of the consortium as a whole, SHORE project as the key project associated with the Helix community as well as visibility of all users who subscribed to the Helix community to improve the ability for users to identify potential partners for collaboration.

Figure 10- Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Community Members

Opportunity Posts: As a primary way for Helix users to search for partners, consortia, coordinators, individual experts, and event attendees, opportunity posts connected stakeholders for further collaboration.

Results Posts: contributed to dissemination and exploitation efforts of the community, including the SHORE consortium, to publish key findings, research results, and public

deliverables, and created potential cooperation and knowledge transfer between different groups.

Direct messaging and comment features: Members could send and receive direct messages and comments on their opportunity posts, facilitating communication among registered users and supporting dialogue on potential collaborative research activities.

4.3. Recommender Engine

CrowdHelix's recommender engine provides efficient and targeted matchmaking between stakeholders. This is made possible through keywords associated with specific expertise sought in opportunities and results posted on the Helix. When setting up their profiles, each individual stakeholder adds relevant research keywords that reflect their expertise. These keywords are then matched with the opportunity keywords, allowing the system to generate matchmaking suggestions for prospective collaborators. The Helix moderation team completes the matchmaking process by sharing the related opportunities with the most suitable stakeholders on the platform. As a result, the recommender engine ensures that stakeholders receive the most relevant opportunities aligned with their research areas and interests, promoting collaboration, knowledge exchange, and stakeholder engagement.

4.4. Mission Ocean Helix Activity

Throughout the SHORE project, the Helix has experienced a significant increase in engagement and content generation aimed at raising awareness, sharing partnership requests, and offering expertise among stakeholders in areas related to Mission Ocean. This includes sharing collaboration opportunities, domain expertise, and promoting ongoing projects and initiatives. Regular updates have highlighted funding calls, research outcomes, policy developments, and relevant events, with a strong focus on topics directly related to Mission Ocean themes, ocean literacy, and SHORE objectives and activities.

For quality assurance, all posts submitted to the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix are moderated and curated by an internal team of experts. This ensures that the content is relevant to the community, appropriately categorised, and enriched with relevant keywords to enhance matchmaking through the recommender engine.

Events have also been central to the Helix's engagement strategy, with numerous webinars and external conferences promoted through the platform to provide members with networking opportunities offered by the Mission Ocean, sister projects and other stakeholders. To date, **84 collaboration opportunities, 22 results, and various Mission Ocean-related events have been shared with the Helix community.**

The following are recent opportunity posts on the Helix. They focus on forming consortia, sharing expertise, seeking collaborators in specific areas, and offering expertise and opportunities arising from ongoing projects and event dissemination.

<p>17 days ago</p> <p>Registration Open "Mission Ocean in Practice: From Policy Priorities to Strong Proposals" Online Training Event, May 26, 11:00 AM CEST</p> <p> Dr. Burcu Kiper for CrowdHelix</p> <p>Seeking expertise: ocean literacy, marine biology, environmental education +3 more</p> <p>Seeking collaborator: Event Attendee</p> <p>Water and 2 more</p>	<p>5 days ago</p> <p>Blue Senses: Discover the Ocean with Your Senses Limassol, 18-24 May 2026</p> <p> Dr. Burcu Kiper for CrowdHelix</p> <p>Seeking expertise: ocean literacy, Mission Ocean and Waters, Ocean conservation +2 more</p> <p>Seeking collaborator: Event Attendee</p> <p>Water and 2 more</p>	<p>27 days ago</p> <p>Competition for the "Ocean & Waters Ambassador of the Year" Awards</p> <p> Dr. Burcu Kiper for CrowdHelix</p> <p>Seeking expertise: BLUE GROWTH, ocean literacy, Mission Ocean and Waters +3 more</p> <p>Seeking collaborator: Community Participant</p> <p>Water and 2 more</p>	<p>1 month ago</p> <p>Shore Webinar: Implementing Open Calls under Mission Ocean: Lessons Learned Online, Thursday, May 7th, 5 pm CEST</p> <p> Dr. Burcu Kiper for CrowdHelix</p> <p>Seeking expertise: ocean literacy, marine biology, Cascade funding management +5 more</p> <p>Seeking collaborator: Event Attendee</p> <p>Water and 2 more</p>
<p>1 month ago</p> <p>Registrations are open for the MSCA-PF MasterClass @UNIVPM 2026 Edition!</p> <p> Dr. Marco Berzano for Marche Polytechnic University</p> <p>Seeking expertise: Digital Health, computational biology, Marine Ecology +26 more</p> <p>Can act as: Coordinator</p> <p>Health and 2 more</p>	<p>1 month ago</p> <p>Seeking to join consortium as project partner in upcoming HORIZON-CL6-2026-01-CIRBIO-11</p> <p> Dr. Declan Colbert for Technological University of the Shannon Midlands Midwest</p> <p>Seeking expertise: BLUE GROWTH, marine organisms, Collaborative project +6 more</p> <p>Can act as: Expertise, Work Package Leader, Consortium Partner</p> <p>Materials and 2 more</p>	<p>1 month ago</p> <p>Seeking Membrane Technology Expert Organisation to join existing consortium</p> <p> Panos Psarolidas for Triaina Synergies P.C.</p> <p>Seeking expertise: Bioremediation, Biomembranes, Decontamination +2 more</p> <p>Can act as: Work Package Leader, Consortium Partner</p> <p>Water and 2 more</p>	<p>2 months ago</p> <p>The European Climate Pact annual event 2026: Together in Action</p> <p> Dr. Burcu Kiper for CrowdHelix</p> <p>Seeking expertise: ocean literacy, climate action, environmental education +1 more</p> <p>Seeking collaborator: Event Attendee</p> <p>Mission Climate and 2 more</p>

Figure 11- Recent Collaboration Opportunities on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

<p>CrowdHelix in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Black Sea</p> <p>Handbook for teachers: SHORE's Teaching Routes</p> <p></p> <p>Facilitating blue education in the classroom Discover a step-by-step learning pathways that help teachers deliver ocean and water literacy activiti...</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Read more</p> <p>Edit</p>	<p>CrowdHelix in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Black Sea</p> <p>Waves of Change: A consolidated review of best practices, activities, and results from SHORE-funded school projects</p> <p></p> <p>The "WAVES OF CHANGE" report presents a comprehensive synthesis of best practices, activities, and results from the SHORE network's school-led proj...</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Read more</p> <p>Edit</p>
<p>CrowdHelix in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters</p> <p>SHORE Project Regional Hub Reports</p> <p></p> <p>With the aim to facilitate the implementation of project schools, increase awareness within local communities about ocean-related issues, and empow...</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Read more</p> <p>Edit</p>	<p>CrowdHelix in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters</p> <p>Blue Skills: Preparation and Participation Processes (Train & Take Part)</p> <p></p> <p>Blue Skills: Preparation and Participation Processes study includes the base analyses in the regional areas to understand the current status of oce...</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Read more</p> <p>Edit</p>
<p>AIR Centre in Mission Climate, Mission Ocean & Waters</p> <p>WaveLinks.EU repository of innovative solutions</p> <p></p> <p> Technology demonstrated in situ</p> <p>WaveLinks is a dynamic digital platform designed to connect, map, and amplify the Mission Ocean ecosystem, accelerating collaboration and innovatio...</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>CrowdHelix in Mission Ocean & Waters, Aquaculture, Black Sea</p> <p>On Efficient Data Sharing for Planetary Digital Twins: Distributed Microplastic Monitoring</p> <p></p> <p>Massive garbage patches within all oceanic gyres have garnered global attention, underscoring microplastic pol- lution as an emerging concern. Vari...</p> <p> Funded by the European Union</p>

Figure 12- Recent results posts on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

Mission Ocean & Waters

Increasing the awareness of ocean literacy among society, with a specific focus on empowering students as agents of change

[Leave](#)
[View Helix](#)

Latest Updates
Opportunities | Results | Events

Mission Ocean in Practice:...

Online
May 26, 2026, 01:00 PM -
May 26, 2026, 02:30 PM

[Learn more](#)

What to expect from Horizon...

Online
Jun 11, 2026, 01:00 PM -
Jun 11, 2026, 02:30 PM

[Learn more](#)

Figure 13- Recent events on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

HORIZON-CL6-2026-01-CIRCBIO-11
Harnessing the unique properties of marine organisms to deliver sustainable blue bio-based products
[View call info](#)

Deadline:
September 17, 2026

Project types:
HORIZON-RIA HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions

[Project Proposal](#)

Dr. Declan Colbert
 for Technological University of the Shannon Midlands Midwest
1 day once in Materials, Mission Ocean & Waters, Aquaculture

[Follow](#)
[Send Message](#)

Seeking to join consortium as project partner in upcoming HORIZON-CL6-2026-01-CIRCBIO-11

Can act as:

Work Package Leader
Consortium Partner
Individual Expert

Seeking expertise:

Blue growth

Marine organisms

Collaborative project

Aquatic biomass

Marine biology

Bio based materials

Environmental and marine biology

Marine organism

Algae cultivation

We are looking to join a consortium with a coordinator already forming around this call. Ideal partners would complement our processing and materials expertise with upstream marine biology and algae cultivation capability, synthetic biology for biomass or extraction optimisation, life cycle and sustainability assessment, and industry partners in packaging, agriculture, or consumer goods with a clear interest in bio-based material substitution.

Know a potential collaborator for this opportunity?
Declan wants to find the best possible collaborator worldwide for this opportunity, and so has opened it to individuals from outside the CrowdHelix Network.

Share this opportunity

Figure 14- Details of Opportunity Posted on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix

Figure 15-Collaboration in real time as comments and direct message to the opportunity post

Figure 16- Number of Posts and Subscriptions to the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix over the years

4.5. Webinars, Clustering Activities & Helix Events

As part of the Helix engagement strategy, a series of webinars, clustering events, and Helix events were organised between 2025 and 2026. These events played a crucial role in community building, sharing project results, and promoting collaboration across various sectors. The objectives of these events included:

- Mobilising different stakeholder groups in line with the SHORE project's overall objectives
- Facilitating exchange of knowledge, twinning, best practice exchanges and collaboration with other Mission Ocean Initiatives
- Raise awareness on ocean literacy and sustainability topics through inclusive and practical events.

The table below summarises the activities organised by CHX in close collaboration with the SHORE project coordinator, communication manager, consortium partners, representatives from sister projects ProBleu and BlueLights, as well as other stakeholders, including research and technology organisations, schools, EU-funded project representatives, and international organisations. Over 331 participants from various stakeholder groups attended the events and gained insights from the diverse topics and themes presented.

Table 2-Events Organised

Event Title	Date	Event Theme	Stakeholders Engaged	No of Attendees
Promoting Ocean Literacy and the Funding Sources to Make it Happen	20 March 2025, online	Launching the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix and presenting funding opportunities and best practices for promoting ocean literacy across Mission Ocean initiatives	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, civil society, EU-funded projects (REMEDIES and ProBleu), international organisations (World Ocean Council), the general public	55
How Schools Can Become Agents of Change for Ocean Literacy	13 November 2025, online	Showcasing school-led initiatives across Europe as catalysts for ocean literacy and sustainability, in support of the EU Mission Ocean education objectives.	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, civil society, and winners of the Ocean & Waters Ambassador of the Year Award, the general public	74
Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools	28 January 2026, online	Presenting innovative digital platforms developed to support teachers in integrating ocean themes into classroom education.	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, civil society, media, EU-funded projects (ProBleu and BlueLights), the general public	55

Twinning & Best Practices: Expanding the Network of European Blue Schools	26 March 2026, online	Exploring how twinning and best practice sharing can strengthen and expand the Network of European Blue Schools across Europe.	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, civil society, international organisations/initiatives (Network of European Blue Schools), EU-funded projects (ProBleu and BlueLights), the general public	63
Implementing Open Calls under Mission Ocean: Lessons Learned	7 May 2026, online	Examining the design and delivery of open calls and cascade funding mechanisms as tools for reaching schools and local actors at scale.	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, industry, EU-funded projects (ProBleu and BlueLights), the general public	25
Mission Ocean in Practice: From Policy Priorities to Strong Proposals	26 May 2026, online	Practical guidance on building competitive proposals for Mission Ocean funding, drawing on hands-on experience from multiple Horizon Europe projects.	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, industry, EU-funded projects (AXOLOTL), the general public	59
Making Results Last: Exploitation and Sustainability in Mission Ocean Projects	15 June 2026, hybrid	Exploring exploitation strategies and sustainability pathways for Mission Ocean projects, with a focus on maintaining collaboration beyond the project lifetime.	Scientific Community: research and technology organisations, education institutes, civil society, policy makers, EU-funded projects (ProBleu and BlueLights), the general public	<i>To be added to the SHORE final report</i>
Total Number of Participants: 6 Online Events and 1 Hybrid Event				331

4.5.1. First Mission Ocean and Waters Helix Event: Promoting Ocean Literacy and the Funding Sources to Make it Happen (20 March 2025)

Following the phase 1 activities for the Helix, including aligning the Helix with SHORE, onboarding consortium partners, stakeholder mapping, and developing the engagement strategy, the first Mission Ocean & Waters Helix event took place online on **March 20, 2025, attracting 98 registrants and 55 attendees**. The event, marking the official launch of the Helix community as part of the SHORE project, aimed to explore the challenges and opportunities associated with the Mission Ocean initiatives. The event was organised to allow Helix members from universities, research organisations,

and industry partners interested in the Mission Ocean to discuss how these initiatives can help address the urgent issues facing marine and freshwater ecosystems.

To this end, the key objectives of the event were:

- Engage with experts working at the forefront of marine research and the blue economy.
- Discover funding opportunities designed to promote ocean literacy
- Discover how the Mission Oceans and Waters Helix can support collaboration across research, business and society
- Understand how to participate in a growing network committed to restoring our oceans and waters.
- Learn about transformative projects driving ocean sustainability.

The event was moderated by the CHX events and impact acceleration teams, with the following invited speakers:

- **Maëva Voltz**, SHORE project communication manager, Euronovia, France
- **Uroš Novak**, Leader of the research group for Bioplastics, Biocomposites, and Zero-waste Technologies, National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia
- **Lisa Simone de Grunt**, Director of Programmes, World Ocean Council
- **Gennadi Lessin**, Marine Systems Modeller, Plymouth Marine Laboratory, Representative of ProBleu Project
- **Paul McKenna**, Head of Membership Operations, Crowdhelix Limited

Maëva Voltz gave an overview of the SHORE project objectives and activities. **Uroš Novak** presented the **REMEDIES** project, a Mediterranean Lighthouse initiative focused on reducing microplastic pollution and nutrient losses upstream, sharing lessons learned about the effectiveness of open calls for reaching communities, and highlighting that over 1.3–5 million people have been reached through the project's innovative technologies and regional partnerships.

Lisa Simone de Grunt shared the World Ocean Council's work in fostering Corporate Ocean Responsibility across maritime industries through programmes, events such as the Sustainable Ocean Summit, and EU-funded projects, while also running an interactive audience quiz on ocean knowledge.

Gennadi Lessin presented the **ProBleu** project's efforts to expand the European Blue Schools Network, detailing how schools can apply for grants of up to €10,000, access a multilingual catalogue of teaching resources, and become certified blue schools, with an upcoming funding call opening the following day.

Paul McKenna demonstrated the Crowdhelix platform and its Mission Ocean and Waters Helix community, which connects researchers, builds project consortia, and disseminates project results, with SHORE as its key project.

CHX and Euronovia collaborated to promote, communicate, and disseminate the Helix event through the SHORE project's social media channels, website and the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix. A recording of the event was subsequently disseminated to all registered attendees and made publicly available via the SHORE project's [YouTube](#) channel and within the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix.

A feedback survey was shared with the participants at the end of the event, with the following results:

- **Overall satisfaction with the event:** 4.47 out of 5, indicating that the webinar was exceptionally well-received by the participants.
- **Content and relevance of the event:** 4.5 out of 5, suggesting the topics and materials were well chosen and valuable to the audience.
- **Speaker(s) rating:** 4.79 out of 5, the highest rated aspect of the event, showing a highly effective and engaging presentation

Figure 17-Promotional Materials for Social Media

Figure 18-Recording of the 1st Helix Event on SHORE Community's YouTube Channel

SHORE

Andrea Petrea
for Crowdfunder
Updated 1 yr. Once in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Black Sea

Registration open | Promoting Ocean Literacy and the funding sources to make it happen | Online, 20 March

Seeking collaborator:
Event Attendee

Seeking expertise:
Water Funding Ocean literacy Blue economy Mission ocean and waters Mission ocean

Crowdfunder will celebrate the launch of its Mission Oceans and Waters Helix by hosting a free online webinar showcasing the funding sources to promote ocean literacy.

Title: Promoting Ocean Literacy and the funding sources to make it happen
Date: 20th of March
Time: 11 am CET
Registration: <https://bit.ly/4i7mg6X>

Key speakers include; Lisa Simone de Grunt, World Ocean Council, Director of Programmes, and Uros Novak, Coordinator of the project REMEDIES, and BioApp platform, and research Group Lead at the National Institute of Chemistry.

Lisa Simone de Grunt will provide an overview of the concepts behind ocean literacy while Uros Novak will highlight the opportunities provided by Mission Ocean initiatives and describe the best practices associated with funding applications.

Their expertise aligns with the ambition of Crowdfunder's Mission Oceans and Waters Helix, which seeks to become an international open innovation platform bringing together experts from academia, education, industry, and civil society. Its goal is to enhance the health and sustainability of our oceans and waters by increasing the awareness of ocean literacy and fostering knowledge sharing, collaboration, and innovation.

Participants will hear from leading experts involved in transformative projects, including the SHORE project, which empowers students as agents of change for ocean literacy, alongside other notable initiatives contributing to sustainability in the blue economy.

More information and registration at: <https://bit.ly/4i7mg6X>

SHORE IS AN EU MISSION RESTORE OUR OCEANS AND WATERS PROJECT. Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101112815.

Funded by the European Union

Figure 19-1st Helix Event Announcement on the Mission Ocean & Waters and Aligned Helix Communities

4.5.2. How Schools Can Become Agents of Change for Ocean Literacy (13 November 2025)

The webinar on practical examples of school-led initiatives in ocean literacy took place online on November 13, 2025. **The event had 177 registrants with 74 attendees during the live session.** Its aim was to highlight how schools can serve as catalysts for ocean literacy and sustainability. The event shared information about the SHORE project's efforts to develop and disseminate blue curricula, as well as ways in which teachers and students can help protect marine and freshwater ecosystems through educational projects.

The event was moderated by the CHX events and impact acceleration teams. The keynote speaker was **Prof. Dr Afşın Çetinkaya, coordinator of the SHORE project at Yıldız Technical University**, who presented the project in detail. **Associate Professor Jean Marie Graic from the University of Padua** also contributed by discussing the work being done within the SHORE Country Hubs. Additionally, the event recognised the winners of the Ocean & Waters Ambassador of the Year Award. Coordinators from two award-winning schools presented their projects: **"Blue Heritage, Blue Future"** from Fatih Sultan Mehmet Primary School in Türkiye and **"From Rain to Ocean: Sustainable**

Water Management and Microplastic Reduction” from İzmir Karşıyaka Zeki Şairoğlu Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School in Türkiye.

CHX and Euronovia collaborated to promote, communicate, and disseminate the event through the SHORE project’s social media channels, website and Mission Ocean & Water Helix. A recording of the event was subsequently disseminated to all registered attendees and made publicly available via the SHORE project’s [YouTube](#) channel and within the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix.

A feedback survey was shared with the participants at the end of the event, with the following results:

- **Overall satisfaction with the event:** 4.71 out of 5
- **Content and relevance of the event:** 4.65 out of 5
- **Speaker(s) rating:** 4.79 out of 5

Survey results indicate that the event was very relevant to attendees and that its content and speakers were well received.

Figure 20-How Schools Can Become Agents of Change for Ocean Literacy Webinar Helix Announcement

Figure 21-How Schools Can Become Agents of Change for Ocean Literacy Webinar Social Media Promotion Materials

Figure 22- How Schools Can Become Agents of Change for Ocean Literacy Webinar Recording

4.5.3. Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools (28 January 2026)

The next event in the series was carried out online on January 28, 2026, with the aim of showcasing three innovative digital platforms developed as part of the sister projects: SHORE, ProBleu and BlueLights. **The event had 116 registrants with 55 attendees during the live session.** Participants were introduced to the [SHORE Community Platform](#), the [ProBleu Catalogue of Teaching Aids](#), and the [BlueLightS Knowledge Hub](#). The webinar highlighted how each platform supports project-based learning, curriculum integration, and student engagement on topics related to oceans and water. Together, these resources create a rich ecosystem for educators, offering everything from ready-to-use lesson materials to community features and project support tailored for both primary and secondary schools.

The event was moderated by the CHX events and impact acceleration teams. Presentations were given on various platforms by the following representatives: **Zaynab Cook**, RKSoft/SHORE Project; **Luca Jendrek**, Sea Teach/BlueLightS; and **Elisabet Bonfill Molina**, Institute of Marine Science/ProBleu Project.

CHX and Euronovia collaborated to promote, communicate, and disseminate the event through the SHORE project's social media channels and website. A recording of the event was subsequently disseminated to all registered attendees and made publicly available via the SHORE project's [YouTube](#) channel and within the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix.

SHORE

Dr. Burcu Kiper
for CrowdHelix
4 ay önce in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Citizen Science

Following Send Message

Shore Webinar: Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools | Online, Wednesday January 28, 5 pm CET

Seeking collaborator:
Event Attendee

Seeking expertise:
Ocean literacy Environmental education Environmental and marine biology
European network of blue schools Primary and secondary education

The Shore Project consortium invites all stakeholders to join our upcoming webinar, "Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools."
•Date & Time: Wednesday 28, 5 pm CET
•Location: Online
•Registration link: <https://events.crowdhelix.com/...>

"SHORE: Empower Students as the Agents of Change", "ProBleu: Promoting Ocean and Water Literacy in School Communities", and "BlueLightS: Enlightening Future Schools to Deliver Blue Sustainability in Europe" are three sister projects funded by the Horizon Europe Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters. These initiatives aim to promote blue education and ocean literacy in schools.

Figure 23-Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools Webinar Helix Announcement

Figure 24-Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools Webinar Promotional Materials

Figure 25- Empowering Blue Education: Platforms for Ocean Literacy in Schools Webinar Recording

4.5.4. Twinning & Best Practices: Expanding the Network of European Blue Schools (26 March 2026)

The following event continued the clustering activities among SHORE, ProBleu, and the BlueLights project by focusing on twinning and best practices, drawing on the projects' practical tools, training, and opportunities that support schools in embedding blue education and ocean literacy into everyday teaching and learning. **The event had 135 registrants with 63 attendees during the live session.** These best practices included teacher training and structured online courses, as well as hands-on citizen science activities that bring students closer to real-world ocean and water challenges. The event also emphasised how [the Network of European Blue Schools](#) support collaboration, twinning and the exchange of proven approaches across countries and school communities.

The event was moderated by the CHX events and impact acceleration teams. The keynote speaker was **Dominika Wojcieszek**, Project Manager and Blue Schools Officer with the Network of European Blue Schools (NEBS). Following her, there were spotlight presentations by sister projects: **Dr. Nail Üçyol** from the Turkish Marine Research Foundation discussed the SHORE project's teacher training for Blue Education; **Irene Gkotsi**, project manager at IDEC, presented BlueLightS' e-training course for teachers on blue education; and **Aisha Nankanja**, a researcher at Earthwatch, highlighted the citizen science initiatives of the ProBleu project. CHX and Euronovia collaborated to promote, communicate, and disseminate the event through the SHORE project's social media channels and website. A recording of the event was subsequently disseminated to all registered attendees and made publicly available via the SHORE project's [YouTube](#) channel and within the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix.

SHORE

Dr. Burcu Kiper
for Crowdfunder
2 ay önce in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Citizen Science

Following Send Message

Shore Webinar: Twinning & Best Practices: Expanding the Network of European Blue Schools | Online, Thursday March 26, 5 pm CET

Seeking collaborator:
Event Attendee

Seeking expertise:
Citizen science Ocean literacy Marine biology Environmental education
Environmental biology Primary and secondary education Network of european blue schools
European blue schools

The Shore Project consortium invites all stakeholders to join our upcoming webinar, "Twinning & Best Practices: Expanding the Network of European Blue Schools"

- Date & Time: March 26, 5 pm CET
- Location: Online
- Registration link: <https://events.crowdfunder.com/...>

Figure 26- Twinning & Best Practices Webinar Helix Announcement

Figure 27- Twinning & Best Practices Webinar Promotional Materials

Figure 28- Twinning & Best Practices Webinar Recording

The event feedback survey received 5-star reviews from all participants for their overall satisfaction. Attendees praised the speakers' knowledge and presentations, as well as the content's relevance to the target audience. Additionally, free-form feedback highlighted the event's impact and value, with participants expressing strong interest in the information shared.

4.5.5. Implementing Open Calls Under Mission Ocean: Lessons Learned (07 May 2026)

The subsequent event shifted the SHORE project consortium's focus to implementing open calls under Mission Ocean. All three sister projects, SHORE, ProBleu, and BlueLights, have been utilising cascade funding to support schools within their respective initiatives. The clustering group that planned the activity facilitated a valuable knowledge exchange session to share lessons learned from the SHORE, ProBleu, and BlueLights projects. In this regard, the event looked beyond theory to discuss how to design and deliver open calls that are clear and impactful for both applicants and funders. **The event had 60 registrants with 25 attendees during the live session.**

During the keynote presentation by Oriane Georges, the F6G Blue Economy Synergy Master, participants received a structured overview of how cascade funding operates within the Mission Ocean context. This was followed by the sister project representatives' presentations on the implementation of open calls. **Pedro Costa**, Head of the Education Unit at INOVA+, discussed the design processes and eligibility criteria for calls under the ProBleu project. **Olga Anagnostaki**, project manager at IDEC, shared valuable lessons learned and practical guidance for applicants participating in the BlueLights open calls. Additionally, **Joanna Makocka**, EU project manager at F6S, and **Milana Sekulic**, communication manager at F6S, reflected on their experiences implementing open calls and the outcomes achieved within the SHORE project.

The screenshot shows a LinkedIn event announcement for 'Shore Webinar: Implementing Open Calls under Mission Ocean: Lessons Learned' on Thursday, May 7th, 5 pm CEST. The event is hosted by Dr. Barcu Kiper. It is seeking collaborators, event attendees, and expertise in areas such as Ocean literacy, Marine biology, Cascade funding management, Environmental education, Open call management, Environmental biology, Primary and secondary education, and Cascade funding. The announcement includes a registration link, a description of the webinar's focus on cascade funding, and a list of key takeaways for attendees.

Shore Webinar: Implementing Open Calls under Mission Ocean: Lessons Learned | Online, Thursday, May 7th, 5 pm CEST

Seeking collaborator:

Event Attendee

Seeking expertise:

Ocean literacy Marine biology Cascade funding management Environmental education

Open call management Environmental biology Primary and secondary education Cascade funding

•Date & Time: May 7th, 5 pm CEST
 •Location: Online
 •Registration link: <https://revent.uk/en/CrowdHel...>

"SHORE: Empower Students as the Agents of Change", "ProBleu: Promoting Ocean and Water Literacy in School Communities", and "BlueLights: Enlightening Future Schools to Deliver Blue Sustainability in Europe" are three sister projects funded by the Horizon Europe Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters. These initiatives aim to promote blue education and ocean literacy in schools.

This session will share practical experience from implementing open calls under Mission Ocean, with a focus on cascade funding (Financial Support to Third Parties) as a mechanism to reach schools and other local actors efficiently and at scale. Drawing on lessons learned from the SHORE, ProBleu, and BlueLights consortia, the event will look beyond theory to discuss what it takes to design and deliver open calls that are clear, fair, and impactful—for both applicants and funders.

Join us to:

- Understand how cascade funding mechanisms are used under Mission Ocean to support smaller actors and speed up local impact.
- Learn from practice through implementation insights from SHORE, ProBleu, and BlueLights—what worked well, what created friction, and how processes can be strengthened.
- Identify transferable lessons for designing future open calls: clearer guidance, better support, efficient evaluation, and meaningful impact reporting.
- Bring your questions to an interactive Q&A on practical implementation challenges and solutions.

Figure 29- Implementing Open Calls Under Mission Ocean Webinar Helix Announcement

Figure 30- Implementing Open Calls Under Mission Ocean Webinar Promotional Materials

Figure 31- Implementing Open Calls Under Mission Ocean Webinar Recording

4.5.6. Second Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Event: Mission Ocean in Practice: From Policy Priorities to Strong Proposals (26 May 2026)

The second Mission Ocean & Waters Helix event took place online on May 26, 2026, attracting **97** registrants and **59** attendees. Organised in collaboration with the [Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute](#) and “[From Sky to Seafloor Observation: Achieving Excellence in Oceanic Surveillance and Conservation through deep Learning-AXOLOTL](#)” project, the event provided a practical overview of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”, bridging policy objectives with real project implementation. The session presented how the Mission works beyond the Work Programme, what evaluators are looking for and how to build strong, competitive proposals for Mission Ocean funding. Drawing on hands-on experience from multiple Mission-related projects and coordination activities, the session highlighted key success factors, common pitfalls, and proven strategies for impactful participation into Mission Ocean initiative activities.

The event was moderated by the CHX events and impact acceleration teams, with **Gotellenne Piaton**, Head of Research & Innovation Support Unit (RISU) at the Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI), as the keynote speaker.

The expected impact on participants of the event included:

- A clear(er) understanding of how the Mission operates in practice and how to position within it
- Practical guidance on designing strong, impact-driven proposals
- Insights into what evaluators expect and how to avoid common mistakes based on real experience
- Tips for building effective consortia and engaging stakeholders meaningfully – with specific examples from the SHORE and Axolotl projects

CHX and Euronovia collaborated to promote, communicate, and disseminate the Helix event through the SHORE project’s social media channels and website. A recording of the event was subsequently disseminated to all registered attendees and made publicly available via the SHORE project’s YouTube channel and within the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix.

A feedback survey was shared with the participants at the end of the event, with the following results:

- **Overall satisfaction with the event:** 4,76 out of 5
- **Content and relevance of the event:** 4,80 out of 5
- **Speaker(s) rating:** 4,92 out of 5

Figure 32- 2nd Helix Event Promotional Materials

SHORE

Dr. Burcu Kiper
for Crowdhelix
Updated 2 gün önce in Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Black Sea

Registration Open | "Mission Ocean in Practice: From Policy Priorities to Strong Proposals" | Online Training Event, May 26, 11:00 AM CEST

Seeking collaborator:
Event Attendee

Seeking expertise:
Ocean literacy Marine biology Environmental education Eu missions
Mission ocean and waters Environmental biology

Registration is open for the next Crowdhelix Training Event of 2026!

Title: Mission Ocean in Practice: From Policy Priorities to Strong Proposals
Speaker: Gotelenne Piaton, Teaming Project Manager - Head of RISU
Date: Tuesday 26th May, 2026
Date: 11 am CEST
Location: Online
Registration: <https://events.crowdhelix.com/...>

In partnership with CMMI, the AXOLOTL project (GA 101158669) and the SHORE project (GA 101112815), both funded by the European Union under Horizon Europe, this event provides a practical overview of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030", bridging policy objectives with real project implementation. It will offer insights into how the Mission works beyond the Work Programme, what evaluators are looking for, and how to build strong, competitive proposals.

Figure 33- 2nd Helix Event Announcement on the Mission Ocean & Waters and Aligned Helix Communities

Figure 34- 2nd Helix Event Recording

4.5.7. Making Results Last: Exploitation and Sustainability in Mission Ocean Projects (15 June 2026)

The final clustering activity of the SHORE project will be held in a hybrid format on June 15, 2026, as part of the final SHORE event organised by the project coordinator, YTU, in Istanbul, Türkiye. This event will unite the sister projects ProBleu and BlueLightS, enabling them to share their experiences regarding exploitation and sustainability.

During the session, representatives from all three projects will present how they are advancing their results and continuing collaborations beyond the EU funding period. They will also discuss the tools and platforms available to support and sustain the communities that have been built.

The session will be hosted by CHX on behalf of the SHORE project. Each project will highlight its key achievements and exploitation strategies, with a focus on knowledge transfer, policy engagement, and stakeholder involvement. Additionally, participants

will have the opportunity to see a demonstration of the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix community on the CHX platform.

5. Conclusion

The Mission Ocean & Waters Helix played a crucial role in fostering collaboration and engagement across its platform activity and results. It brought together representatives from complementary EU-funded initiatives, including [REMEDIES](#), [ProBleu](#), [BlueLightS](#), [AXOLOTL](#), [the World Ocean Council](#), [the Network of European Blue Schools](#), as well as members of the wider research, education, civil society and industry communities. This multi-project approach enabled participants to identify connections within the Mission Ocean landscape, share practical knowledge, and strengthen collaborative ties beyond the SHORE consortium. **As of date, the Helix hosts 887 domain experts from 323 organisations across 46 countries; significantly exceeding its target.** The membership typology reflects a broad cross-sectoral composition, including research and technology organisations, SMEs, corporates, associations, and specialist organisations. We can infer that the Helix community successfully attracted stakeholders from across the research and education, innovation and industry sectors. The presence of educational institutions among Helix members, combined with the webinar series that directly showcased school-led initiatives, award-winning projects, and teacher training programmes, ensured that Helix amplified SHORE's impact beyond the research and innovation community, extending its reach to the students and teachers at the heart of the project's mission.

In terms of webinars, clustering and Helix events, **two Helix events and five webinars organised between March 2025 and June 2026 had 331 participants from diverse stakeholder groups**, including research and technology organisations, educational organisations, civil society, industry, international organisations and the general public, which belong to the primary and secondary target groups of the SHORE project. Feedback from participants showed overall satisfaction, content relevance, and speaker quality above 4.5 out of 5, highlighting the quality of engagement delivered through the Helix activities.

The event series also generated concrete connections and outcomes that illustrate the Helix's role as an active facilitator. The first Helix event brought together the various projects in a shared forum for the first time, enabling direct dialogue on ocean literacy approaches. The second event recognised the winners of the Ocean & Waters Ambassador of the Year Award, bringing student and teacher level impact into the Helix's public programme and demonstrating the tangible connection between the platform's stakeholder network and educational outcomes. The clustering sessions with ProBleu and BlueLightS moved beyond information exchange to practical knowledge transfer, with representatives from all three projects sharing eligibility frameworks, applicant guidance, and lessons learned from cascade funding implementation, insights that are now documented within the Helix and available to future Mission Ocean project developers. The final hybrid event in Istanbul, co-organised with the project coordinator YTU, will bring this collaborative thread to a close and mark the transition to the Helix's post-project phase, with a live demonstration of the platform as a sustainability tool for the wider Mission Ocean community.

Platform activity on the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix reinforced engagement outcomes. **A total of 84 collaboration opportunities and 22 results were shared with the community throughout the project**, creating a living repository of expertise offers, partnership requests, and key exploitable results that extend the reach of the SHORE project's outputs beyond traditional dissemination channels. The recommender engine and moderation-driven matchmaking ensured that content reached the most relevant stakeholders, while the direct messaging and comment features enabled real-time dialogue among members.

The activities delivered through the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix over the course of the SHORE project have followed the roadmap below established at the outset of the project.

PHASE 1 – SET UP

Set-up of the Helix and on-Boarding Partners
 Setting up the targeted stakeholders' ecosystem
 Design the strategy to approach the stakeholders
 Connect with sister projects
 Official Launch of the Helix – 1st Helix Event

PHASE 2 – ENGAGEMENT

Strengthen and expand the network and the participation of stakeholders
 Share and disseminate scientific knowledge and KERs
 Organisation of webinars and clustering activities
 Clustering Activities
 Funding opportunities

PHASE 3 – IMPACT & FOREGROUND

2nd Helix Event
 Organisation of webinars and clustering activities
 Technology Transfer and Commercialisation Opportunities
 Seek Funding for Further development
 Policy Advocacy
 Training and Capacity Building

PHASE 4 – AFTER PROJECT

Consider Helix Sponsors/Leaders
 Keep interaction in the Helix to stimulate new proposals and funding opportunities
 Stimulate new scientific debate based on the follow-up of the project
 Attract the attention of policymakers and investors

Figure 35- Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Roadmap

- **Phase 1** encompassed setting up the Helix, onboarding partners, and designing the stakeholder engagement strategy, culminating in the community's official launch at the first Helix event.
- **Phase 2** focused on strengthening and expanding the network through clustering activities, dissemination of scientific knowledge and KERs, and the identification of relevant funding opportunities.
- **Phase 3** is oriented toward impact, foreground and collaboration for future opportunities.
- **Phase 4** activities will involve sustaining interaction within the Helix to stimulate new proposals and are expected to continue beyond the project's lifetime, ensuring the community's long-term vitality.

Looking ahead, the commitment to maintaining the Mission Ocean & Waters Helix for up to 5 years after the SHORE project's conclusion underscores Crowdhelix's

dedication to long-term impact. The community will continue to serve as a knowledge exchange and matchmaking platform for the ocean and waters research and innovation ecosystem, supporting the broader goals of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" and providing a sustainable home for the collaborative relationships and resources generated during the project.

The Crowdhelix Impact Acceleration Team, along with the Helix members, will have the opportunity to share new collaboration opportunities related to the Mission Ocean & Waters themes. This includes updates and announcements about relevant Mission Ocean & Waters calls for proposals, partner searches, projects and their outcomes. Additionally, they will continue to organise events related to Mission Ocean & Waters as needed.

Annex section

1. Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Member Organisations

No	Organisation Name	Organisation Type	Country
1	Dokuz Eylul University	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
2	University of Haifa		IL
3	Ca' Foscari University of Venice		IT
4	Ege University		TR
5	University of Coimbra		PT
6	University of Turku		FI
7	University of Strathclyde		GB
8	Brunel University of London		GB
9	L-Università ta' Malta		MT
10	Universiteit Antwerpen		BE
11	University of Cagliari UNICA		IT
12	Instituto Superior Tecnico		PT
13	NTNU		NO
14	University of Padua		IT
15	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki		GR
16	University of Cape Town		ZA
17	Manchester Metropolitan University		GB
18	Moreforskning AS		NO
19	University of Galway		IE
20	University of Twente		NL
21	Munster Technological University		IE
22	University College London (UCL)		GB

23	Crowdhelix	SME	GB
24	The University of Greenwich	Research and Technology Organisation	GB
25	Durham University		GB
26	University of Essex		GB
27	University of Southampton		GB
28	Turku University of Applied Sciences		FI
29	University of Leeds		GB
30	Middle East Technical University		TR
31	Sabanci University		TR
32	Queen's University Belfast		GB
33	TÁœBÄ°TAK		TR
34	Cardiff University		GB
35	University of Manchester		GB
36	KTH Royal Institute of Technology		SE
37	Hellenic Open University		GR
38	Izmir Katip Celebi University		TR
39	Tampere University		FI
40	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - UnitÁ Valorizzazione della Ricerca		IT
41	AIR Centre		PT
42	University College Cork		IE
43	LEITAT Technological Center		ES
44	Ulster University		GB
45	University of Ljubljana		SI
46	Technion – Israel Institute of Technology		IL
47	University of Groningen		NL
48	Universitat de les Illes Balears	ES	

49	Ozyegin University	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
50	University of Liverpool		GB
51	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid		ES
52	Trinity College Dublin		IE
53	University of Reading		GB
54	University of West Attica		GR
55	University of Manitoba		CA
56	Technological University Dublin		IE
57	University of Witwatersrand		ZA
58	Universidad de Alcalá		ES
59	Universitat Rovira i Virgili		ES
60	CYENS Centre of Excellence		CY
61	UniSMART		IT
62	University of Copenhagen		DK
63	Beia Consult	SME	RO
64	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (CSIC)	Research and Technology Organisation	ES
65	KU Leuven		BE
66	Universita degli Studi di Milano		IT
67	Delft University of Technology		NL
68	IRIS	SME	ES
69	Inspiralia	Specialist	ES
70	University of Cyprus	Research and Technology Organisation	CY
71	University of Bologna		IT
72	Stichting Radboud Universiteit (Radboud University)		NL
73	University of Auckland		NZ

74	University of Otago	Research and Technology Organisation	NZ
75	COFAC/ Lusofona University		PT
76	University of Maribor		SI
77	Stellenbosch University		ZA
78	Ankara University		TR
79	Atatürk University		TR
80	Izmir University of Economics		TR
81	Knowledge Transfer Network Ltd	Associate	GB
82	University of South-Eastern Norway - USN	Research and Technology Organisation	NO
83	National Institute of Biology (NIB)		SI
84	EFUND GROUP SASU	SME	FR
85	KPMG Portugal	Corporate	PT
86	National Institute for Marine Research and Development “Grigore Antipa”	Research and Technology Organisation	RO
87	European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)	Associate	DE
88	EURONOVIA	SME	FR
89	Children's Office University of Vienna		AT
90	Agri-Food and BioSciences Institute (AFBI)	Research and Technology Organisation	GB
91	EU GrantsAccess	Associate	CH
92	Nord University	Research and Technology Organisation	NO
93	Innvotek	SME	GB
94	Vianet Srl		IT
95	Innovation Commercial Pathways		GB
96	Tree Technology / Treelogic		ES
97	Vilnius Gediminas Technical University		LT

98	University of Zurich	Research and Technology Organisation	CH
99	National Institute of Chemistry		SI
100	Tel Aviv University		IL
101	A-TEAM Marketing and Consulting d.o.o.	SME	RS
102	ALLWEB SOLUTIONS S.A.		GR
103	University of Zagreb	Research and Technology Organisation	HR
104	LUT Universities		FI
105	Ben-Gurion University of the Negev		IL
106	International Solid Waste Association (ISWA)	SME	NL
107	McMaster University	Research and Technology Organisation	CA
108	University of Alberta		CA
109	University of Montreal		CA
110	Aarhus University		DK
111	Technical University of Denmark		DK
112	Technische Universität Darmstadt		DE
113	Technical University of Crete		GR
114	Technological University of the Shannon Midlands Midwest		IE
115	Open University of Israel		IL
116	Weizmann Institute of Science		IL
117	University of Ferrara		IT
118	University of Johannesburg		ZA
119	University of Pretoria		ZA
120	Jönköping University		SE
121	Karolinska Institutet	SE	
122	ETH Zurich	CH	

123	HES-SO : UAS Western Switzerland		CH
124	Erciyes University	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
125	İzmir Institute of Technology		TR
126	Yıldız Technical University		TR
127	University of Birmingham		GB
128	Sinop University		TR
129	Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU)		SI
130	Eight Bells Ltd.	SME	CY
131	Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique	Research and Technology Organisation	FR
132	Onepartner Integrated Advisory Services s.r.l.	SME	IT
133	Centre for Process Innovation Ltd (CPI)	Research and Technology Organisation	GB
134	Lithuanian Energy Institute		LT
135	Privanova	SME	FR
136	Prospex Institute	Associate	BE
137	Turkish Marine Research Foundation	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
138	Zoï Environment Network	Associate	CH
139	Central Fisheries Research Institute - Trabzon	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
140	Cargill	Corporate	BE
141	Prague University of Economics and Business	Research and Technology Organisation	CZ
142	The Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI)		CY
143	Impuls Consulting	SME	HR
144	CIMUS - USC	Research and Technology Organisation	ES

145	GeoEcoMar - National Research-Development Institute for Marine Geology and Geoecology	Research and Technology Organisation	RO
146	Fraunhofer IWU		DE
147	LMU Munich		DE
148	Politecnico di Milano		IT
149	University of Nicosia	Corporate	CY
150	Imperial College London	Research and Technology Organisation	GB
151	IDENER.AI	SME	ES
152	Science Business	Associate	BE
153	ANALISIS-DSC	SME	ES
154	European University Cyprus	Research and Technology Organisation	CY
155	Neem Biotech	SME	GB
156	Trilateral Research Ltd		GB
157	University of Sarajevo	Research and Technology Organisation	BA
158	T.E Laboratories Ltd	SME	IE
159	E-institute		SI
160	C3 Systems Consulting		GB
161	IZNAB		PL
162	Prospex		BE
163	Vertech Group		FR
164	Feron Technologies		GR
165	University of Belgrade		Research and Technology Organisation
166	Sustainable Innovation Technology Services Ltd	SME	IE
167	Aspen Waite		GB

168	Paragon Europe	SME	MT
169	DVOKUT-ECRO d.o.o.		HR
170	Agence Thématique de Recherche en Sciences et Technologie	Research and Technology Organisation	DZ
171	mediomix GmbH	SME	DE
172	National Physical Laboratory (NPL)	Research and Technology Organisation	GB
173	Fusion Search	SME	GB
174	Utrecht University	Research and Technology Organisation	NL
175	Academy of Entrepreneurship	SME	GR
176	Mihanografiki LLC		GR
177	Applied Research Solutions (ARS)		BG
178	Emerald Group	Corporate	GB
179	Lapland University Consortium	Research and Technology Organisation	FI
180	B Solutions	SME	ME
181	Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia	Research and Technology Organisation	IT
182	Universidade da Coruã+a		ES
183	ZITEC	SME	RO
184	Scalable Projects		GB
185	Elvesys		FR
186	Immersion		FR
187	Zaz Ventures		BE
188	EN-CO Software Ltd.		HU
189	Tyndall National Institute	Research and Technology Organisation	IE
190	SU Nanotechnology Research and Application Center		TR
191	Cosmos Business Systems SA	SME	GR

192	ELG Carbon Fibre Ltd	SME	GB
193	University of Botswana	Research and Technology Organisation	BW
194	Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina		BR
195	Carleton University		CA
196	Concordia University		CA
197	Dalhousie University		CA
198	The University of British Columbia		CA
199	University of Ottawa		CA
200	University of Waterloo		CA
201	The University of Nottingham		GB
202	Czech Technical University in Prague		CZ
203	Engineering College of Aarhus		DK
204	Escuela Superior Politécnica del Litoral		EC
205	Universität des Saarlandes		DE
206	Dimocritus University of Thrace		GR
207	University of Ioannina		GR
208	University College Dublin		IE
209	Vytautas Magnus University		LT
210	Vilnius University		LT
211	Victoria University of Wellington		NZ
212	University of Medicine and Pharmacy of Bucharest (UMFCD)		RO
213	Ventspils University of Applied Sciences	LV	
214	Universidad de Cádiz	ES	
215	Universidad de Vigo	ES	
216	University of Geneva	CH	
217	Kadir Has University	TR	

218	KoÅs University	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
219	Marmara University		TR
220	Buckinghamshire New University		GB
221	Coventry University		GB
222	University of Portsmouth		GB
223	University of East London		GB
224	Bulent Ecevit University		TR
225	Laval Mayenne Technopole	SME	FR
226	Triaena Synergies P.C.		GR
227	Slot Consulting Ltd.		HU
228	Inbude		DK
229	JUSTINMIND		ES
230	Eindhoven University of Technology	Research and Technology Organisation	NL
231	eBOS Technologies Ltd	SME	CY
232	Centro Tecnológico de la Información y de la Comunicación(CTIC)	Research and Technology Organisation	ES
233	Dell Technologies	Corporate	IL
234	Indigo-Med	SME	GR
235	German Aerospace Centre	Research and Technology Organisation	DE
236	Champalimaud Foundation		PT
237	Returnee Migrant Centre		GH
238	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (APRE)	Specialist	IT
239	Argentina Ministerio de Ciencia Tecnología e Innovacion	Research and Technology Organisation	AR
240	NORCE (Norwegian Research Centre AS)		NO
241	JelTom	SME	HR

242	Virtualware	SME	ES
243	Institut de Recerca Biomèdica Catalunya Sud (IRBCatSud)	Research and Technology Organisation	ES
244	Marine Institute		IE
245	ETAM	SME	GR
246	M&O Partners		BR
247	EurA AG		DE
248	Next Technology Tecnotessile		IT
249	Digiotouch OU		EE
250	ÁšdarÁ;s na Gaeltachta	Specialist	IE
251	WavEC OffSHORE Renewables	SME	PT
252	FederaÃ§Ã£o das Pescas dos AÃ§ores	Specialist	PT
253	Instituto Nacional de Tecnologia Industrial (INTI)	Research and Technology Organisation	AR
254	Xylem Analytics	Corporate	GB
255	Bio Base Europe Pilot Plant	Research and Technology Organisation	BE
256	Tiga Information Technologies	SME	TR
257	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis	Research and Technology Organisation	AT
258	Digital Science	Specialist	GB
259	Greater Copenhagen EU Office	Research and Technology Organisation	BE
260	The Economic Policy Research Foundation of Turkey	Associate	TR
261	Marine Cluster Bulgaria		BG
262	Athens University of Economics and Business - Research Center (AUEB-RC)	Research and Technology Organisation	GR
263	StratÃ©gies Mer et Littoral	SME	FR

264	Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research- Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	Research and Technology Organisation	BG
265	European Marine Board	Associate	BE
266	Organization of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation (BSEC)	Research and Technology Organisation	TR
267	FIGES A.Å¸.	SME	TR
268	Castalia Innovation Ltd		GB
269	Cobre Las Cruces	Corporate	ES
270	BRGM	Research and Technology Organisation	FR
271	BELIT	SME	RS
272	Arquimea Research Center	Research and Technology Organisation	ES
273	RESCOLL	SME	FR
274	Global Factor	Corporate	ES
275	Harmet OÅ¸e	SME	EE
276	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research	Research and Technology Organisation	GR
277	F6S Network Ireland Limited	SME	IE
278	Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (SCSTI SR)	Research and Technology Organisation	SK
279	Centro di Ricerche Europeo di Tecnologie Design e Materiali (CETMA)		IT
280	European Marine Science Educators Association (EMSEA)	Associate	BE
281	IPLUSO - Instituto PolitÅ¸nico da Lusofonia	Research and Technology Organisation	PT
282	Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes		HR
283	The Finnish Geospatial Research Institute (FGI), National Land Survey of Finland		FI

284	EMBL - European Molecular Biology Laboratory	Research and Technology Organisation	GB
285	SmartSol	SME	LV
286	Eurecat - Centro TecnolÃ³gico de CataluÃ±a	Research and Technology Organisation	ES
287	Aleksander Moisiu University Durres		AL
288	The Association of Commonwealth Universities		GB
289	WEglobal	SME	GB
290	Atrium Environmental		DE
291	Università Telematica degli Studi IUL	Research and Technology Organisation	IT
292	MARE NOSTRUM ONG	Specialist	RO
293	RKSOFT	SME	TR
294	Day One	Specialist	IT
295	Net4CO2 CoLAB	SME	GB
296	DigiMV		GB
297	CIIMAR	Research and Technology Organisation	PT
298	AgroTech Plus	SME	KE
299	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn		GB
300	CTIC Technology Research Center	Research and Technology Organisation	ES
301	Beam Digital	SME	IT
302	ORIM Management SL		ES
303	Warrant Hub	Corporate	IT
304	Bloomer House	SME	TR
305	MacAlsiter Elliott & Partners		GB
306	ISOTECH Ltd		GB

307	Ecosistemas Virtuales y Modulares SL (EVM)	SME	ES
308	Danube Delta National Institute for Research and Development Tulcea	Research and Technology Organisation	RO
309	North Anatolian Development Agency	SME	TR
310	Science Crunchers		GB
311	European Aquaculture Technology & Innovation Platform		GB
312	EIT Hub Israel		GB
313	Breda University of Applied Sciences		GB
314	ACTeon		GB
315	Institutul National De Cercetare Dezvoltare Pentru Ecologie Industriala	Research and Technology Organisation	RO
316	Acube Srl	SME	IT
317	Lux Actuaries & Consultants PC		GR
318	infoteam Software		GR
319	Capitole Consulting	Corporate	ES
320	Madrid City Council	Associate	ES
321	Deep Sea Technologies	SME	GR
322	Laser Consult Kft.		HU
323	JV ConnectInn		GB

2. Guidance on the Crowdfelix Platform and Mission Ocean & Waters Helix Account Creation

The image shows two side-by-side panels. The left panel is the 'Create your account' form on the Crowdfelix platform. It includes fields for First name (Sally), Last name (Ride), Email (name@company.com), Organisation (a search dropdown), and Password (password). There is a checkbox for terms and privacy, a blue 'Register' button, and a link for existing users. The right panel is a dark blue promotional banner with the text 'Over 3,600 Opportunities, and counting!' and 'Find your next inspiring collaboration, with thousands of open opportunities posted by other members'. It features a stack of white cards representing project proposals, with the top one titled 'Synthetic Photosynthesis: Engineering Plants to Increase Carbon Sequestration Efficiency' by Dr Carlos Baldwin from ESU. The card shows search filters for 'Soil', 'Carbon', and 'Atmosphere', and role options like 'Coordinator', 'Consortium Partner', and 'Individual Expert'.

Figure 36- Account Creation Form

Consortium members of the SHORE project can create their accounts on the Crowdfelix platform via the sign-up link (<https://platform.crowdfelix.com/register/project-partner>) with their organisational email addresses with the corresponding domain.

Completing Personal Profile

Once users create their accounts, they can complete their profiles in “Settings” on their main page. Profile details include their job title, professional social media account information, a short biography and expertise tags. Adding expertise tags will enable proper profiling on the platform and enable the platform’s AI-powered recommender engine to match them to the most relevant opportunities posted on the platform, as well as the most suitable funding calls.

Figure 37- Example of Profile Settings

Notification Settings

Users have the option to set different email notification settings for the Helixes and receive updates on opportunities posted on the platform immediately, daily or weekly.

Figure 38- Example of Notification Settings

Posting a collaboration opportunity

Platform users can create new collaboration opportunities by clicking on “opportunities” on the main page. The system allows users to create opportunities for a new project proposal or an existing project.

Left Screenshot:

- Header: Crowdhelix
- Navigation: < Back to Opportunities
- Title: Create an Opportunity: Project Proposal
- Progress: 1. Overview 2. Details 3. Description 4. Visibility
- Text: On this page, and the ones that follow, you will be taken through the process of creating a new collaboration opportunity on Crowdhelix step-by-step. If you would like additional information please consult the User's guide, or get in touch with the Crowdhelix team using the Support button below.
- Section: **Who are you posting on behalf of?**
- Text: Choose your organisation and (if applicable) your department or research group.
- Field: *Organisation (Select Organisation dropdown)
- Section: *** Which Helix communities are relevant to your opportunity?**
- Text: Choose up to three Helixes to share your opportunity in.
- Field: (Empty input box with + icon)
- Section: *** Opportunity title**
- Text: e.g. Seeking international collaborators for upcoming Digital Health call
- Field: Add title (input box)
- Button: Next

Right Screenshot:

- Header: Crowdhelix
- Navigation: < Back to Opportunities
- Title: Create an Opportunity: Project Proposal
- Progress: 1. Overview 2. Details 3. Description 4. Visibility
- Text: Your progress will be saved as you submit each page, so you can leave and come back to finish later if you wish.
- Section: **Which roles would you be willing to take in the collaboration?**
- Text: Select all that apply.
- Form: Grid of checkboxes for Coordinator, Work Package Leader, Consortium Partner, Individual Expert.
- Section: *** What expertise are you seeking from potential collaborators?**
- Text: Choose one or more keywords and press enter after each one.
- Field: e.g. Big data, Statistics, Robotics... (input box)
- Section: **Are you targeting a Horizon Europe call?**
- Text: If so, use the box below to search for the call using either its title or its identification code.
- Field: e.g. ICT-38-2020 (dropdown menu)
- Buttons: Back, Next

Figure 39- Opportunity Creation

Opportunity posting steps are summarised below. Users are taken step by step in identifying key elements in their opportunity, such as the roles they would like to take on, the expertise they are looking for from potential collaborators, and specifications of the collaboration as well as the visibility of the opportunity to the network (visible only to the network members), extended network (non-member research and technology organisations) and public (promoted on the Crowdhelix website and social media platforms).

Interacting with the Community

Users can interact with the Helix community via the opportunities post by:

- Sending a direct and private message to the post's author
- Commenting below the opportunity
- Sharing the opportunity with other platform users or a trusted collaborator not yet registered on the platform.

Project Proposal

Prof. Andrea Sabatini
for University of Cagliari UNICA
2 ay önce In Water, Mission Ocean & Waters, Citizen Science

[Follow](#) [Send Message](#)

Expertise offered for the HORIZON-CL6-2026-02-FARM2FORK-08 Call

Can act as:
Work Package Leader Consortium Partner Individual Expert

Seeking expertise:
Advanced big data analysis Citizen science Consortium partner Sah expertise
Consortium building Project coordinator Migratory fish

The DISVA – Section of Animal Biology and Ecology, Laboratory of Freshwater Ecology at the University of Cagliari (Italy) is seeking to join a consortium for the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-CL6-2026-02-FARM2FORK-08: "Advancing basic knowledge and developing tools for sustainable management of key migratory fish species."

We offer advanced expertise on the distribution and population dynamics of the European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*) in Sardinian rivers, along with a long-term dataset on glass eel recruitment. The island of Sardinia, strategically located in the central-western Mediterranean, provides an optimal setting to evaluate both recruitment processes and spawning migrations of adult eels. Our contribution to large-scale in situ biodiversity observations includes experience with innovative monitoring methods and a deep understanding of local fisheries and productive contexts. We also actively support the development of management tools, conservation strategies, and modelling approaches, as well as new initiatives in Sardinia for tagging and releasing silver eels at sea. Our team engages with local stakeholders and promotes citizen science and multi-actor collaboration to support adaptive and sustainable management practices. If you are building a consortium and are looking for experienced partners in eel ecology, freshwater biodiversity monitoring, and migratory fish management, we would be pleased to collaborate. We are open to partnerships and joint proposal development. Contact Andrea Sabatini - email asabati@unica.it

Know a potential collaborator for this opportunity?
Andrea wants to find the best possible collaborator worldwide for this opportunity, and so has opened it to individuals from outside the CrowdHelix Network.

[Share this opportunity](#)

Responses

[Write a response...](#)

Dr. Behrouz Gholamhadi
2 ay önce

Hey Professor. We are interested in participating in calls related to animal feed to test our fine biochar (EBC-certified). Regards, Behrouz

[Reply](#)

Figure 40- Interacting with the community

Users can also interact with the community via the search tool at the top of the platform's main page. Here, they can search for opportunities, organisations, groups, experts, and results.

Figure 41- Platform search tool

Posting Collaborative Research Results

Users can also showcase innovative collaborative research results associated with different Helix communities and projects. The results feature can be accessed on the main page, as shown below.

Figure 42- Results Feature

The steps for publishing results are illustrated in the images below. Users can share their results in up to three Helix communities. They should include details such as the project associated with the result, the result title, the current technology readiness level, relevant links, and a description of the result. Users may include results from any related institutional, local, national, EU-funded, or international projects.

You are currently editing a draft result Discard

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Create a Result

1. Overview 2. Details 3. Description

On this page, and the ones that follow, you will be taken through the process of creating a new project result on CrowdHelix. Results can be at any stage of development, from basic science to a proven system or approach. If you would like additional information please consult the User's guide, or get in touch with the CrowdHelix team using the Support button below.

Who are you posting on behalf of?
Choose your organisation.

*Organisation

* Which Helix communities are relevant to your result?
Choose up to three Helixes to share your result in.

* Result title
e.g. Prototype Virtual Reality controller to support patient rehabilitation

Next

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Create a Result

1. Overview 2. Details 3. Description

Your progress will be saved as you submit each page, so you can leave and come back to finish later if you wish.

Which existing project would you like to associate? *
Please select the project your Result relates to from the list below. If the project is not listed, you can add basic information about it. Other users will be able to visit links related to the project you have chosen.

Current Technology Readiness Level *
Please indicate the result's current level of technological maturity. If you are unsure please estimate this for now, as you will be able to edit and update it at any time.

Add links
Please add any relevant web links that can provide information about the result.

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*** Describe your result**
Please provide a description of the result below. You could consider including information about its development stages, its target audience and/or market, its key stakeholders, and/or any plans to ensure its impact and uptake.

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Submit

Figure 43- Results Posting Steps

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